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Introduction to the guidelines for repositories and registries on exposing repository trustworthiness status and FAIR data assessments outcomes

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Executive Summary

To reach an intended aim of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to be a research data environment populated with digital objects that present a range of desirable characteristics, including FAIRness, a complex partnerships of actors and agents, performing activities and delivering services, are required to be involved in creating processes and activities across the research (meta)data lifecycle and ecosystem, from the initial conception of a research goal, through data creation and collection and deposit in a repository, to eventual reuse. The ability to cooperate, interoperate, and deliver services to end users depends on mutual trust between service providers and digital object creators, depositors, users, and funders.

The intention of the guidelines, introduced here, is to increase the transparency of information about metadata and data services and the digital objects they hold by exposing it in ways that enable humans and machines to harvest, exchange, and use the information. Thus providing a foundation for interoperability, establishing trustworthiness, and allowing the (meta)data service to improve the current state of connections between the services, including registries, and the information they can exchange at the organisational and the digital object level.

There are no common approaches for collecting and making available the results of FAIR assessments. However, it is clear that there is a need to keep such results accessible, to share them with others and to indicate the quality of a research output. These guidelines will present potential methods to advertise assessment results.

The implementation of FAIR principles does not always depend on the practices and processes undertaken in a Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) at digital object level, but rather on the implementation of policies at organisational level. It further can be difficult to create FAIR-compliant metadata because common standards do not provide the appropriate properties. The guidelines, and suggested approach presented here, aim for making information available at the (meta)data provider and digital object levels to increase transparency, provide evidence, and refine FAIR assessment. They are meant to enable better integration and reuse in complementary services. Because of this purpose, it is planned within FAIR-IMPACT to implement and link the guidelines in a prototype.

The prototype will play a crucial role as a proof of concept, bringing the drafted ideas to life and the purpose of the guidelines. It will showcase the fundamental features, interactions, and user experience, thus helping stakeholders evaluate its viability. This proof of concept allows for early identification of potential flaws, gaps, or improvements, and to adjust the subsequent development when linking services. The mission is to link them in a core demonstrator, that is kept small and simple, still proving the assumption it will foster actuality, trustworthiness, and better (semi-)automation of exposing information.

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Terminology

Terminology/Acronym	Description
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESRC	Economic and Social Research Council
FDS	Future Data Services
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
LTDP-TF	EOSC Association Long Term Data Preservation Task Force
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

2 Introduction

This document by the FAIR-IMPACT project presents the rationale and approach to the development of guidelines and a prototype that will expose information at the (meta)data service and digital object levels in a transparent and uniform way. The aim of this work is to facilitate better connections with registries and discovery portals to be established. This work takes place in FAIR-IMPACT as part of work on *metrics, certification, and guidelines*, specifically in a task about *FAIR data and code in FAIR-enabling Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDR)*. This document is the first output of this line of work and it depicts the initial plan and scope for the work in the project.

The aim of the guidelines is to increase the transparency of information about repositories and other (meta)data services and the digital objects they hold, or link to, by exposing it in ways that enable humans and machines to harvest, exchange, and use the information. This provides an essential foundation for interoperability, demonstrating trustworthiness and allowing the (meta)data service to improve its presence in the wider environment and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Specifically in this envisioned line of work, we will focus on two areas of information:

- Information related to the trustworthiness of a data service and the transparent exposure of information that helps to inform such a status,
- Information about the FAIRness of the digital objects held by the data service, in the form of assessment results.

This report will depict the plans for the creation of the guidelines and the prototype that will be developed to implement them. It will present the scope of the work, the current rationale and considerations, as well as the activities and future steps throughout the project. The report is open for community input until September 14th 2023¹ and will feed into the design of the first iteration of the guidelines that will be published in October 2023.

¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-materials-community-review>

3 The design of the metadata guidelines and prototype

3.1 Rationale

This work aims to improve the current state of connections between (meta)data services, including registries, and the information they can exchange at the organisational and the digital object level. Improving the ease of connecting these different strands of information can enable a more seamless discovery of (meta)data services and their objects, and better harvesting and exchange of information to relevant registries and discovery portals. Analyses of the current landscape show some issues and inconsistencies in the way that, for example, repository homepages, data catalogues, and digital object ‘landing pages’ are expressed and categorised. This can complicate the way such repositories and their contents are indexed and showcased in registries and discovery portals, and obstruct large scale comparisons and analyses.

There are many characteristics of data services and digital objects that are important to a wide range of stakeholders to which they may wish to have easy access, either directly at the data service, or through registries and discovery portals. The focus in this work is specifically on characteristics and information related to the trustworthiness of a (meta)data service and the transparent exposure of information that helps to inform such a status, as well as information about the FAIRness of the digital objects held by the data service, in the form of assessment results. This report suggests a basic RDF² metadata model, using standards such as DCAT³, to expose this information in a transparent and uniform manner, to improve and simplify the way in which this information can be expressed, interpreted and shared. The interactions, as depicted in Figure 1, move bidirectionally between the digital object and data service as well as the data service and registry. A validation authority can verify one or more items of information or characteristics of the repository or digital object and actively push or let a (meta)data service pull the necessary information.

Figure 1. The main interactions of relevance to the guidelines and prototype.

² <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#quality-information>

The guidelines that are introduced in this document will also be implemented in a prototype during the FAIR-IMPACT project. We will use an iterative approach to the development of the guidelines and prototype, improving them based on community input and findings from the prototype testing. Our aim is to include the relevant stakeholders ((meta)data service providers, registries, discovery portals) at large to ensure that the outputs fit with the needs and developments of the community. This work will also contribute to the development of a Network of FAIR-enabling Trustworthy Digital Repositories⁴, as it will facilitate a more uniform and interoperable exposure of repository information and characteristics.

3.2 The purpose of the guidelines

Figure 2. The relationship between information about a (meta)data service described as metadata and its validation by external third parties.

⁴ Philipp Conzett, Ingrid Dillo, Françoise Genova, Natalie Harrower, Vasso Kalaitzi, Mari Kleemola, Amela Kurta, Pedro Principe, Olivier Rouchon, Hannes Thiemann, & Maaïke Verburg. (2022). Towards a European network of FAIR-enabling Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs) - A Working Paper (v2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034314>

Figure 2 presents the high-level relationship between information about the **functions** or **activities** about a (meta)data service that an organisation may choose to expose, and the potential uses of such transparent information by third parties, including for interoperability, validation or as evidence for assessment. An external **validation authority** may assess the available evidence to deliver an evaluation such as the potential trustworthiness of a service by which an end user may answer the question *“Does this service meet my minimum criteria to trust what it provides?”*. The remainder of this section describes and elaborates on concepts from Figure 2 with the defined entities in bold text.

A metadata or data service has **characteristics** (e.g. an address, contact details, a preservation policy, etc.) which can be exposed as metadata and often exists on a website for the service. It will also have services, or **functions** that consist of **processes**, which in turn, consist of a series of **activities**. Again these can be described and exposed as metadata. However, can a user of the service trust the assertions made in the metadata? Are the contact details correct, is there an up-to-date preservation policy, or are the FAIR metrics scores asserted still valid? This kind of information, which is essential for facilitating trust in a service, is currently often lacking or difficult to discern.

The trust in the assertions made may be provided by a third party, a **validation authority**, who provides a **test** and **evidence** for the **asserted value** which may be valid for a fixed period to a **time limit**. For example, CoreTrustSeal⁵ could provide transparent evidence that the data service provider has a valid preservation policy as part of its certification of the data service, which is valid for a fixed time (in the case of CoreTrustSeal, 3 years). If the service provider exposes FAIR assessment results for its digital objects, it is important to know which tool was used to create the score. Moreover, knowledge of how the score was created and which metrics were used may be essential to some users, for example when comparing research software tools and resources. Therefore, a FAIR assessment tool such as F-UJI⁶ is the **validation authority** on the scores it generates and could provide evidence in a transparent fashion with additional information on metrics used, software versioning, and domain-specificity of the metrics (elaborated on in section 3.4).

For example, workflows at re3data or CoreTrustSeal (or any other organisation) can either accept assertions, validate them through third parties (**validation authorities**), or undertake some local validation (human or machine-mediated).

The approach to the information exposed about each organisations’ function or activity would depend on the intended use. A repository can choose what to expose depending on a variety of criteria, for example:

- Whether the function activity is applicable to the service (e.g. preservation information is not relevant to organisations that don’t offer preservation).
- The intended consumers (e.g. to support registry updates, certification processes, or communication with funders, depositors, or users).

⁵ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

⁶ Anusuriya Devaraju, & Robert Huber. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4063720>

For each function or activity the information exposed broadly falls into⁷ :

- Free-text assertions: statements about the organisation in response to descriptive criteria about the required information.
- Controlled assertions: selections from ontologies or controlled vocabularies.
- Evidence Artefacts: e.g. links to policies on rights management, lists of licences, preservation plans, or workflows.

Depending on the information provided and the purpose of the consumer, one or more of the following actions could be selected in response to the presented information:

- Accept assertion: assertion is accepted without further validation.
- Direct machine-actionable validation of assertion: given that the assertion is machine-testable.
- Machine-actionable validation of assertion through a third party: given a third party can be pointed to as the authority on the information asserted.
- Validate assertion through human action: given the assertion is not machine-testable.
- Validate assertion through a mixture of human and machine action: to ensure the content or quality of the supplied information.

Trustworthiness is never perfect. However, by including evidence by trusted third parties the resulting knowledge graph for a (meta)data service provides transparency upon which a decision can be made and acted upon, be that by a human agent (researcher) or increasingly machine-agents.

3.3 The added value of guidelines

Exposing machine-actionable metadata about a (meta)data service is an additional effort for the service and therefore there must be benefits for the service provider, their user communities and others. This section described some potential examples of such benefits currently identified.

Resources registries, be they domain-specific or more general, are an obvious user and harvester of machine-actionable metadata that will give their community of users better insight into digital objects of interest to their community of users. Clearly, the metadata published and harvested must conform to an agreed format, thus guidelines are required for the exposure of the information about the service provided. An additional benefit is that such metadata could be further aggregated by other registries, for example by the EOSC Marketplace, from other ERIC-based registries. There are obvious direct benefits for (meta)data services to have increased findability within the research ecosystem and potentially a broader user base. However, more importantly, in a landscape of many registries and web services all publishing information about a service, it would be possible for the (meta)data service to simply update any information in one location and have it be replicated in all other locations the information is called on. It would even be possible for

⁷ These items reflect the response types to CoreTrustSeal applications.

the service's own website to utilise the published metadata to update information for those arriving there, perhaps via Google. A registry does not need to harvest all the information, as it can provide access to the **evidence** for **asserted values** from the linked knowledge graph of the **validation authorities**.

Some funders, including the European Commission, require grantees to deposit selected research data with trustworthy repositories⁸. Formal certification by a **validation authority** is a good source of **evidence** about the overall trustworthiness of a given service and its **functions**, but it is not the only means of determining trustworthiness. Transparency about the repository service is just as important to help data stewards and researchers to make an informed decision about where they deposit their data and whether they have trust in the service. However, it can be hard to know what to look for to inform a decision on whether a repository is trustworthy and, as such, data stewards and researchers will need guidance and support to help them make an informed choice. There is potential to incorporate guidance such as the FAIR-IMPACT guidelines into existing questions about data storage that are included in most data management plan (DMP) tools. By incorporating guidance into the DMP tools directly, data stewards and researchers will be better supported to make informed choices about data deposit from the earliest stage of their research.

If the guidelines are also incorporated by repository registry services such as re3data⁹ and FAIRsharing¹⁰ using a wider range of **evidence** sources, there is potential to build in functionality to recommend repositories from within DMP tools, thus aiding the researchers in a task they would prefer not to have. Moreover, this use of these guidelines and the published metadata may also be used to aid the completion of applications for certification by a certification body (**validation authority**) as well as making the process of certification easier, or even automated, for the certification body when the information they require is published transparently and not buried in a website (see the next section for more details). Therefore, the guidelines must be flexible enough to allow the addition of published information about the (meta)data service that is of value to validation authorities to obtain.

Anyone can perform a FAIR assessment of a digital object if they have the URI of the landing page or endpoint. However, if the (meta)data service undertakes an assessment of a digital object and publishes the results of this, then the **evidence** from the assessment tool creator (**validating authority**) can also be accessed. This information could also provide more detailed information about the metrics, method, versioning, and **time limit** of the results. This becomes important with digital object type and domain-specific differences in metrics¹¹ applied, such that the user can evaluate the context of the FAIR assessment. A (meta)data service provider may wish to take this further by publishing improvements over time to FAIR assessment results and thus the guidelines could support multiple instances of the metadata assertion and the evidence associated in a transparent fashion. Furthermore, it would be interesting to evaluate if it is possible to use published metadata to help generate FAIR

⁸ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines>

⁹ <https://www.re3data.org>

¹⁰ <https://fairsharing.org/>

¹¹ Robert Huber, Maaïke Verburg, Mike Priddy, Hervé L'Hours, Joy Davidson, & Hannah Mihai. (2023). D5.1 Implementing metrics for automated FAIR digital objects assessment in a disciplinary context (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7784119>

Implementation Profiles (FIP)¹² and if so, what guidelines would be needed as this could be a useful benefit for (meta)data service providers.

These are just a few examples of how a published knowledge graph about a (meta)data service may be used and where guidelines may be required in ensuring a consistent approach and the inclusion of evidence and validation authorities to add trustworthiness and transparency. As we advance with testing the guidelines through the prototype implementation (see section 3.5), these potential examples will develop into more accurate and tested use cases.

3.4 Exposing trustworthiness and transparency

The EOSC seeks to be a research data environment populated with digital objects that present a range of desirable characteristics, including FAIRness (see next section). The ability to achieve this goal depends on actions across the research (meta)data lifecycle and ecosystem from the initial conception of a research goal, through data creation and collection and deposit in a repository, to eventual reuse. These outcomes depend on a wide range of data and metadata skills, products, and services, sometimes delivered through complex partnerships of actors and agents, involved in creating processes and activities. The ability to cooperate, interoperate, and deliver services to end users depends on mutual trust between service providers and digital object creators, depositors, users, and funders.

For repositories that offer active long-term preservation services, a number of standards exist that support the assessment of their fitness to deliver services, framed as ‘trustworthiness’¹³. These Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) standards include a German national standard¹⁴, an ISO standard¹⁵, and the CoreTrustSeal. The 16 CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Repository Requirements and associated certification emerged from a Research Data Alliance (RDA)-endorsed process¹⁶ that has been supported by a number of EOSC-related efforts^{17,18}. The CoreTrustSeal addresses TDR criteria at a low-barrier entry level, the so-called ‘core’ category of certification. Because the CoreTrustSeal depends on repository self-assessments, supported by public evidence that is reviewed by peers, transparency is a key factor in its delivery and success. The reduced number of requirements and lack of on-site audits, in comparison to ISO-standards, necessarily reduces the complexity, cost, and rigour of CoreTrustSeal. However, the dependency on transparency presents advantages beyond the certification process. The public results of each successful

¹² <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

¹³ Trust is inherent and critical to all research infrastructure stakeholders. The concept of evaluating ‘trustworthiness’ seeks to identify key factors that support assertions of trust between parties.

¹⁴ Nestor seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives:

https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Zertifizierung/nestor_Siegel/siegel.html

¹⁵ ISO 16363: <https://www.iso.org/standard/56510.html>

¹⁶ RDA Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/repository-audit-and-certification-dsa%E2%80%93wds-partnership-wg/outcomes/dsa-wds-partnership>

¹⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Turning FAIR into reality – Final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

¹⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Jones, S., Aronsen, J., Beyan, O. et al., Recommendations on certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC – , Genova, F.(editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/127253>

CoreTrustSeal certification contribute to a growing body of public self-assessment statements and supporting evidence. This transparency provides a resource for additional analysis of applications, peer-learning, and communicates relevant information to TDR depositors, users, funders, and partners.

The desirable outcomes of such a transparent process benefits the TDR community and their users. However, equivalent criteria, assessments, certifications, and bodies of information do not currently exist for the wider range of data and metadata service providers that are necessary for a successful EOSC.

At the point of data and metadata reuse it is important to understand the provenance of a digital object in terms of its unique identifier, associated persons and organisational entities, and historical processing steps¹⁹. In assessing the quality and value of a digital object for reuse it is also beneficial to understand the level of care a repository or other (meta)data service has provided for the object, and what level of care the object will receive in the future. This information informs the researcher selecting objects to work with, and informs decisions about where subsequent work based on the original objects could be deposited.

The levels of care given to data and metadata²⁰ can range from simple retention to initial curation at the point of deposit to achieve some level of desirable characteristics (e.g FAIRness). In addition, a TDR may offer services to ensure that data and metadata retain these characteristics over time despite changes to the technological environment or to the needs of the user community. This ‘active preservation’ is undertaken in addition to retention guarantees and initial curation at the point of deposit.

The levels of retention, curation and preservation offered by a (meta)data service, alongside other information about the functions and activities they undertake, may be recorded in a registry (including re3data for repositories) or used to assess compliance and offer certification (including CoreTrustSeal). But not all (meta)data services self-identify as repositories (necessary for inclusion in re3data) and not all repositories offer long-term preservation (necessary to be in scope for CoreTrustSeal assessment). While re3data offers a transparent schema²¹ of repository information, and CoreTrustSeal provides an open process of community comment for revisions through RDA²², multiple other criteria for repositories and (meta)data services exist.

3.5 Repository functions and activities

In an assessment of CoreTrustSeal, FAIR-IMPACT partner the UK Data Service²³ concluded that all CoreTrustSeal Requirements with the exceptions of *ReUse* and *Preservation* would be generally applicable to any organisation offering services around data and metadata, not

¹⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

²⁰ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Discussion Paper (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6908019>

²¹ <https://www.re3data.org/schema>

²² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/coretrustseal-maintenance-wg>

²³ The UK Data Archive (UKDA) (<https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>) leads the multi-partner UK Data Service (<https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>), UK Service Provider to the CEESDA ERIC. The UKDA is CoreTrustSeal certified.

exclusive to repositories offering long-term preservation²⁴. The UK Data Service undertook a more wide-ranging crosswalk²⁵ of repository and data service criteria as a part of its contributions to FAIR-IMPACT, the EOSC Association's Long Term Data Preservation Task Force (LTDP-TF²⁶), and the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) funding body's Future Data Services (FDS²⁷) Programme that is mediated by the ESRC²⁸. This crosswalk integrated criteria from a range of extant standards, requirements and criteria from a range of global efforts, including the CoreTrustSeal, National Science & Technology Council²⁹, National Institutes of Health³⁰, and COAR³¹. It also includes relevant outputs from FAIR-IMPACT's predecessor project FAIRsFAIR³² that addressed the FAIRness of data services³³ and a capability-maturity model for FAIR-enabling Trustworthy Digital Repositories³⁴. The crosswalk demonstrated a strong alliance with the existing 16 CoreTrustSeal Requirements³⁵, but also identified a number of other data services characteristics. From this crosswalk exercise, 29 functions and activities³⁶ were identified for data services. Not all of these functions and activities will be significant for a TDR certification process, but they indicate areas where transparency of (meta)data services transparency has value. Figure 3 below depicts the functions and activities identified and their alignment with the CoreTrustSeal Requirements; the functions with borders (orange) align directly with CoreTrustSeal.

²⁴ L'Hours, Hervé, & Bell, Darren. (2023). UK Data Service (UKDS) Response to the CoreTrustSeal Curation & Preservation Levels Discussion Paper (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828046>

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7690658>

²⁶ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation>

²⁷ <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-offer/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/future-data-services/>

²⁸ Economic and Social Research Council <https://www.ukri.org/councils/esrc/>

²⁹ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/05-2022-Desirable-Characteristics-of-Data-Repositories.pdf>

³⁰ <https://sharing.nih.gov/data-management-and-sharing-policy/sharing-scientific-data/selecting-a-data-repository>

³¹ Confederation of Open Access Repositories:

<https://www.coar-repositories.org/coar-community-framework-for-good-practices-in-repositories/>

³² <https://fairsfair.eu/>

³³ Koers, Hylke, Herterich, Patricia, Hooft, Rob, Gruenpeter, Morane, & Aalto, Tero. (2020). M2.10 Report on basic framework on FAIRness of services (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5473015>

³⁴ Hervé L'Hours, Ilona von Stein, Jerry deVries, Linas Cepinskas, Joy Davidson, Patricia Herterich, Robert Huber, & Benjamin Jacob Mathers. (2021). M4.3 CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling, Capability and Maturity (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5346822>

³⁵ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

³⁶ L'Hours, Hervé, & Bell, Darren. (2023). Repository & (Meta)Data Services Activities & Functions Overview (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689090>

Figure 3: Repository & (meta)data Services Functions & Activities.

Taken from: L'Hours, Hervé, & Bell, Darren. (2023). Repository & (Meta)Data Services Activities & Functions Overview (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689090>

For a larger version of this Figure, see the Appendix.

At present, a (meta)data service could be required to deliver information about these organisational characteristics to a variety of audiences and parties (re3data, CoreTrustSeal, depositors, users, funders, etc.) for a variety of purposes (registry inclusion, certification, service-level transparency, interoperability, etc.).

One simplistic use case would be for the (meta)data service to deliver self-declared certification information (e.g. “we have CoreTrustSeal”) to a registry (e.g. re3data). A slightly more sophisticated version of that use case, as mentioned above, would be for re3data to validate such a self-declared piece of information directly and to use the CoreTrustSeal as an authoritative source to validate the information. Each of these use cases would support basic user interface functionality such as “show me all TDR certified repositories”, which, with additional information such as disciplinary speciality, could help a researcher deposit their outputs in a repository mandated by their funders.

The repository could achieve some of these results by submitting information directly to re3data or CoreTrustSeal. But if there were a mechanism for a repository to declare information transparently to multiple consuming agents there would be a number of clear benefits. The repository would reduce administrative overhead and control the source of their organisational metadata, including accuracy and frequency of updates. This would

allow re3data to pull currently available information about organisations, or allow CoreTrustSeal to pull certification-relevant information directly from applicants. CoreTrustSeal applicants are asked about third party dependencies for their services, and these other products and services providers could usefully expose supporting information relating to clients' and partners' TDR applications. In addition to these specific use cases, increased transparency at the organisational level (and object level, see section 3.4) has the potential for use in the wider data graph of connections between works, people, repositories, and wider organisations (see e.g. DataCite Commons³⁷). The information exposed could include data services' approach to handling rights, persistent identifiers, complex data citations and sensitive data and has the potential for inclusion in other mechanisms such as machine-actionable Data Management Plans (DMP) that incorporate recommended repositories.

The proposed guidelines would place the (meta)data service in control of its own information and permit multiple other organisations to develop streamlined business processes on top of it.

The CoreTrustSeal Requirements remain a key benchmark against which future work should be mapped and aligned, but it is logical to include a broader range of perspectives on what information (meta)data services, including repositories and registries, should expose transparently. As CoreTrustSeal has a broad user base and an existing revision process mediated through the RDA, the FAIR-IMPACT project will explore the elaboration model (initially proposed by FAIRsFAIR³⁸) as a way of integrating these additional functions and activities, while avoiding a confusing array of overlapping criteria.

The initial focus of FAIR-IMPACT work will be to identify the range of transparent metadata to be exposed and the most appropriate structure and content of that metadata. It is not intended in this suggested approach that the exposure on any particular metadata would be enforced or mandated. Any required elements would be requested depending on the needs of consuming applications (e.g. a repository registry or discovery portal).

As noted above, a federated ecosystem of (meta)data services often depends on a range of complex partnerships. A wide range of transparent information at the organisational level would support trust, cooperation, and interoperability in the scientific ecosystem. Some information, such as the levels of retention, curation, and preservation provided are valuable at the organisational level, but not sufficient. A repository may offer a variety of different service levels for different digital objects that it holds; this includes the provision of initial FAIR-enabling curation or the assurance of long term FAIR-enabling as part of active preservation. Ideally, the service level information would also be attached to each digital object. The exposure and assessment of FAIRness at the digital object level is explored in the next section of the document.

³⁷ <https://commons.datacite.org/>

³⁸ See section 5.4 of: Hervé L'Hours, Ilona von Stein, Frans Huigen, Anusuriya Devaraju, Mustapha Mokrane, Joy Davidson, Jerry de Vries, Patricia Herterich, Linas Cepinskas, & Robert Huber. (2020). M4.2 Draft Maturity Model Based on Extensions and-or Additions to CoreTrustSeal Requirements (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5471568>

Initial recommendations:

- The proposed guidelines must place the **(meta)data service in control of its own information** and permit multiple other organisations to develop streamlined business processes on top of it.
- It is beneficial for a (meta)data service to assess the internal information available against the needs of potential consumers and reformat accordingly to **maximise consistency and machine-actionability**. This includes the publication of relevant evidence information such as mission statements, licence information, and preservation policies.
- The exposure of any particular metadata **must not be enforced or mandated**. Any required elements would be requested depending on the needs of consuming applications.

3.6 Exposing digital object FAIR assessment

As the FAIR principles have become more widely recognized by the scientific community in recent years, there has also been an increasing demand for ways to measurably verify the implementation of the FAIR principles. This has also increased the importance of metrics and tools that make this possible for a wide range of users, and a number of such tools are now available for different types of research outputs³⁹. These include tools that attempt to evaluate FAIRness in an automated way as well as questionnaire based self-evaluation tools. These different execution styles are one of the reasons that assessments can lead to completely different results, which illustrates the difficulties for FAIR assessment and depends on a variety of factors and preconditions. First, the implementation of FAIR is relevant to both humans and machines. However, humans and machines have completely different perspectives on digital objects. While machines depend on metadata being as standardised as possible, humans are easily able to recognize them even in unstructured information. This explains the sometimes considerable differences between FAIR evaluations that are performed automatically and those that are based on self-assessments.

Moreover, all FAIR tools are based on different interpretations of FAIR. This is because the FAIR principles are quite general. Thus, in recent years, attempts have been made to derive metrics from the FAIR principles, which in turn have been used to design practical tests for assessment tools. These metrics and tests can also be very different, which can result in varying results that are not easily comparable, even in tools with similar execution types. This current state of the FAIRness assessment tool landscape has already been pointed out several times⁴⁰.

³⁹ See, for example, a non-exhaustive list of tools available at: <https://fairassist.org/>

⁴⁰ See, for example: Sun, C., Emonet, V., & Dumontier, M. (2022). A Comprehensive Comparison of Automated FAIRness Evaluation Tools. In SWAT4HCLS (pp. 44-53).

Therefore, in addition to visually well-presented and user-friendly representation of digital objects on the web, it is crucial to provide metadata in a machine-readable way. This can easily be achieved via common web standards, such as embedding metadata in HTML or providing links to metadata according to signposting conventions. Care should be taken here to use cross-domain metadata standards such as schema.org⁴¹ or DCAT to reach as many audiences as possible. In general, providing metadata that is of high quality and as rich as possible using common web standards will also lead to good results for all FAIR tools.

The implementation of FAIR principles does not always depend on the practices at record (digital object) level, but rather on the implementation of policies at organisational level. It further can be difficult to create FAIR-compliant metadata because common standards do not provide the appropriate properties (e.g. links to data files to allow for machine-testable assertions). Moreover, for a variety of FAIR criteria, there are a myriad of different interpretations possible (e.g. defining 'rich' metadata, or a 'valid' persistent identifier) even at the cross-domain level⁴². It is therefore a good practice to use standards like schema.org or DCAT that allow rich, domain-agnostic descriptions. In addition to such standards, domain-specific formats should also be offered in a way that search engines can also find them. Here, the use of the signposting conventions or the provision via content negotiation is recommended⁴³.

Since all FAIR assessment tools and their underlying metrics look at slightly different aspects of the original FAIR principles and the digital objects it evaluates, it is recommended to use several of these tools to get the most complete impression of the FAIRness of any given unit. The following approach might be beneficial:

- First, one should get a rough overview of the **accessibility and preparation** of an object to be tested.
- After that, it is useful to use a **self-assessment tool** to highlight and understand the human aspect(s) of facilitating FAIR digital objects
- Then, use an **automated tool** (e.g. F-UJI) to test the machine-friendliness of the offering.

In general, however, it is recommended that evaluations that go beyond individual objects be embedded in a multi-stakeholder consultation process, involving not only object owners and developers, but also evaluation tool providers and developers. This allows for a bidirectional iterative process of improvement, in which the tested objects can become more FAIR and, at the same time, the assessment tool(s) can be optimised if necessary.

The identified disparity in FAIR assessment tool results as described above has led to a desire in some areas for a dedicated governance structure⁴⁴. However, it is questionable whether

⁴¹ <https://schema.org/>

⁴² See this FAIRsFAIR commentary on 'baseline' issues with the FAIR principles: Hervé L'Hours, Ilona von Stein, Mustapha Mokrane, Jessica Parland-von Essen, Jerry de Vries, Frans Huigen, Anusuriya Devaraju, Joy Davidson, & Benjamin Mathers. (2020). FAIR Principles: Baseline Comments. (02.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6472149>

⁴³ Wilkinson, Mark D, Sansone, Susanna-Assunta, Grootveld Marjan, Nordling, Josefine, Dennis, Richard, & Hecker, David. (2022). FAIR Assessment Tools: Towards an "Apples to Apples" Comparisons. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7463421>

⁴⁴ Wilkinson MD, Sansone SA, Méndez E et al. Community-driven governance of FAIRness assessment: an open issue, an open discussion [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]. Open Res Europe 2022, 2:146 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.15364.1>

this approach is realistic or can scale with the requirements, given the multitude of possible multinational and multidisciplinary actors⁴⁵. Therefore, we recommend instead providing the means to calibrate FAIR assessment tools as well as to verify their results. This requires a harmonisation of the output formats of these tools as well as the creation of a set of standardised test scenarios in which the expected behaviour of the assessment tools is defined on the basis of reference objects. A first good approach to this was developed in the Apples to Apples initiative by the EOSC Task Force on FAIR Metrics & Data Quality⁴⁶, where a set of tests for the behaviour of assessment tools against signposting was developed. In addition, it is clearly about time to define a precise baseline definition (minimum expected metadata standards, elements, metadata delivery methods) of the FAIR principles that can serve as a benchmark for a cross-domain FAIR implementation. This can then be easily extended to discipline-specific as well as object type-specific needs.

To date, there are no common approaches for collecting and making available the results of FAIR assessments. However, it is clear that there is a need to keep such results accessible at least in the medium term and to share them with others and to indicate the quality of a research output. There are a number of proposals on how to advertise assessment results, for example via badges, but these badges are only valid for a specific state. This is because FAIR results can change. For example, if the underlying test parameters are changed, i.e. the metrics and tests as well as the algorithms of the test tools. Therefore, a FAIR badge should already make clear some explicit information about the tool metrics that were used. In addition, badges should always link to a publicly accessible FAIR web page or digital object where the test result is presented in detail. At a minimum, the following metadata should be made available about assessment results:

- assessment date
- target object identifier
- metric (including information on the version)
- name and version of the assessment tool

In addition, badges should be tamper-proof and, for example, embed this and other metadata in a hidden machine-readable way (see e.g. OpenBadge).

Ideally, these metadata as well as the FAIR assessment result are made available using existing standards. For example the Data Quality Vocabulary may be used which offers “dq:QualityMeasurementDataset” which may provide the metadata mentioned above using the PROV Vocabulary⁴⁷.

In order to effectively link these assessment results with the tested objects in the long term, other measures are possible in addition to badges. For example, these results themselves could be marked with a persistent identifier (PID) and archived in the long term in a suitable archive. Furthermore, such FAIR assessment PIDs could be embedded in the metadata of

⁴⁵ See FAIR-IMPACT project response to the EOSC Governance publication: Maaïke Verburg, Mike Priddy, Robert Huber, Clement Jonquet, Neil Chue Hong, Daniel Garijo, Xení Kechagioglou, Joy Davidson, Ingrid Dillo, & Vasso Kalaitzi. (2023). FAIR-IMPACT project response to "Community-driven governance of FAIRness assessment: an open issue, an open discussion" (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848127>

⁴⁶ Wilkinson, Mark D, Sansone, Susanna-Assunta, Grootveld Marjan, Nordling, Josefina, Dennis, Richard, & Hecker, David. (2022). FAIR Assessment Tools: Towards an "Apples to Apples" Comparisons. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7463421>

⁴⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o>

digital objects. This could be done via suitable relation types or provenance information of the object. Metadata formats such as DCAT recommend the use of specialised vocabularies, such as the Data Quality Vocabulary⁴⁸, for this purpose. Thus, a "dqv:hasQualityMetadata" property could be used to refer to a FAIR assessment result as part of a "dqv:QualityMetadata" record published e.g. as part of a DCAT Dataset. In schema.org, on the other hand, the "sdo:aggregateRating" property could be used for this purpose in a schema.org/Dataset.

Further work is required to decide on best practices to achieve the transparent and richly informative exposure of FAIR assessment results. The measures proposed here for the harmonisation of FAIR assessment tools as well as those for the archiving, exchange, and linking of FAIR assessment results certainly still require some discussion and ideally collaboration in an international environment. FAIR-IMPACT is currently working to create a harmonious overview of different FAIR assessment tools and their mapping to the original FAIR principles to aid this line of work. This resource will be shared once completed.

Initial recommendations:

- To improve FAIRness, **multiple evaluation tools** should be used that support both machine and human-friendly implementation of FAIR principles. Ideally, the process is embedded in a consultation process.
- To harmonise FAIR evaluators, we recommend providing appropriate **annotated test datasets** against which these tools can be calibrated and verified.
- Results of FAIR assessments can be made recognizable to humans using OpenBadge based **badges** that should visually identify the tool used and its version, as well as the metric used.
- For machine-readable embedding of FAIR evaluation results in metadata, we recommend the use of **existing standards** such as the Data Quality Vocabulary in combination with schema.org or DCAT.
- FAIR assessment results linked with these badges or metadata links should be made available via the Data Quality Vocabulary standards and should include a **minimum set of metadata** which include date, assessment target, metric used and name and software version of the testing tool.

⁴⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv/>

3.7 Implementation through the prototype

The guidelines and suggested approach presented in this document aim for making information available at the data provider and digital object level to increase transparency, provide evidence, and refine FAIR assessment. They are meant to enable better integration and reuse in complementary services. Because of this purpose, it is planned within FAIR-IMPACT to implement and link the guidelines in a demonstrator.

The prototyping plays a crucial role in bringing the drafted ideas to life, yet it will not be a single software or service instance. The prototype is envisioned to be a small sample setup, with different infrastructures and services involved. It shall serve as a preliminary model for demonstration of the guideline implementation. It shall showcase the potential of the concept described above. When it comes to adoption of the guidelines, it is important to understand that this is not limited to a single service or setup. Instead, the sample implementation of the guidelines shall act as a connector, bridging different services together towards creating a cohesive and functional whole. The gathered ideas and concepts in this line of work will be transformed into a tangible representation that is envisioned to help stakeholders to better understand the concept and its feasibility. By providing hands-on experience, the prototype shall allow for experimentation, feedback, and refinement in an iterative approach, leading to a clearer vision of the overall concept. This covers all aspects from technical integration to use cases building on top.

The prototype serves as a proof of concept, illustrating the core functionality and purpose of the guidelines. It will showcase the fundamental features, interactions, and user experience, helping stakeholders evaluate its viability. This proof of concept allows for early identification of potential flaws, gaps, or improvements, to adjust the subsequent development when linking services and breaking up information silos. The goal is not to define new standards, services, or technologies, but rather built up on a broad foundation of matured concepts and technologies like upcoming RDA recommendations (DRAWG⁴⁹), RDF and semantic artefacts, as well as outcomes from the FAIRsFAIR project such as the reference implementation of a FAIR Data Point⁵⁰. This mission is to link them in a core demonstrator, that is kept small and simple, still proving the assumption it will foster actuality, trustworthiness, and better (semi-)automation of exposing information.

Standardisation is required at multiple levels of the prototype. This includes the prototyping of a standardised output of FAIR assessment results using the Data Quality Vocabulary⁵¹ (DQV) as well as a standardised FAIR metrics definition output using DQV terms. As mentioned above this standard can be used to link FAIR assessment results with assessed data sets via DCAT and is recommended by the W3C as one of the 'Data on the Web Best Practices'⁵².

⁴⁹ RDA Data Repository Attributes Working Group:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-20th-plenary-meeting-gothenburg-hybrid/data-repository-attributes-working-group-drawg>

⁵⁰ Claudia Behnke, Kees Burger, Yann le Franc, Wim Hugo, Pekka Järveläinen, Jessica Parland-von Essen, & Gerard Coen. (2021). D2.6 First reference implementation of the data repositories features (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5362027>

⁵¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv>

⁵² <https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/>

As a core structure, DCAT Version 3 shall be the minimum requirement to enable exploration of (meta)data services in the prototype. It is supposed to be extended by optional metadata properties to cover the needs by the research data management services as certification authorities, assessment tools and discovery services.

The iterative 3-step-cycle-implementation will include:

1. **Define and publish** metadata by the data service itself. This includes the organisational and digital object level. The desired metadata will depend on the use case at hand.
2. **Basic mapping** and the reuse of the metadata in a single service (e.g. F-UJI).
3. **Validating** the evidence (using the different options described above).

All stakeholders, from data provider, over (meta)data services to complementary registries and authorities, are envisaged to be part of the demonstrator. Thus it is expected to gain insights and ideas for improvement and added values, so the prototyping is scheduled as an iterative process that involves constant feedback and refinement. This iterative approach ensures that the final proof of concept delivered in this project will align with our expectations, user demands, and technological feasibility. By integrating information on data services and digital objects in services for certification, discovery, and assessment, the prototype shall showcase how these services can work together seamlessly to achieve the common goal. This interconnectivity enables stakeholders to envision the potential of an interlinked ecosystem and contribute with their own use cases and value propositions.

The planned testing of the prototype will start with the embedded organisations in the dedicated FAIR-IMPACT task. It is planned to expand the test-bed for the prototype in collaboration with Work Package 2 *'Engagement, adoption and implementation'*, through the mechanism of the open calls for (financial) support run there. Data services will have the opportunity to interact with the demonstrator there, exposing their metadata and providing feedback on feasibility of the model. We will aim to have a well-balanced test-bed of data services interact with the demonstrator during the course of the project, to ensure the guidelines and implementation of them are aligned with different types of organisations (e.g. more and less advanced with regards to trustworthiness and FAIR implementation, different disciplines, contexts, and sizes, etc.).

4 Conclusions and next steps

The initial focus of this FAIR-IMPACT work will be to identify the range of metadata to be exposed for transparency and trustworthiness of a TDR, and the most appropriate structure and content of that metadata. It is not intended in this suggested approach that the exposure on any particular metadata would be enforced or mandated. Any required elements would be requested depending on the needs of consuming applications (e.g. a repository registry or discovery portal or a validating authority). The guidelines, and suggested approach presented in this document, aim to make information available at the data provider and digital object levels to increase transparency, provide evidence, and refine FAIR assessment. They are meant to enable better integration and reuse in complementary services. However, placing the (meta)data service provider in control of its own information will be a key principle of the guidelines and permitting multiple other organisations to build streamlined business processes on top of it.

The prototyping will play an essential role in creating an environment to bring the concepts presented here to life, yet it will not be a single software platform or service instance. It shall serve as a preliminary model for demonstration of the guideline implementation.

Further work is required to decide on best practices to achieve the transparent and richly informative exposure of FAIR assessment results. The measures proposed here for the harmonisation of FAIR assessment tools as well as those for the archiving, exchange, and linking of FAIR assessment results require some discussion and ideally collaboration in an international environment.

This document is the starting point in the creation of the guidelines to increase the transparency and trustworthiness of information about (meta)data services and the digital objects they hold. The aim in publishing the concepts and background, before a full set of guidelines are instigated, is to garner community input. After the gathering of initial feedback from interested parties, this will be integrated into the first version of the Guidelines for Repositories and Registries on Exposing Repository Trustworthiness status and FAIR Data Assessments Outcomes. There will be a small number of iterations of the guidelines developed over the next two years, each incorporating feedback and testing with the prototype involving (meta)data repositories and candidate registries.

Appendix - Figure 3: Repository & (meta)data Services Functions & Activities

Taken from: L'Hours, Hervé, & Bell, Darren. (2023). Repository & (Meta)Data Services Activities & Functions Overview (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689090>

